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Analysis Of Psychological Mechanisms Of Developing Attention Qualities And Methodological Approaches To Their Formation

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Annotation: This article analyzes the psychological mechanisms of developing attention qualities and methodological approaches to their formation. The main characteristics of attention - stability, mobility, distribution and volume - are highlighted from a scientific and psychological point of view, and the role of neurophysiological processes, the interaction of perception and thinking, and the motivational factors of the individual in their development is analyzed. The article also provides scientifically based conclusions about the effectiveness of methods used to form and strengthen attention, including interactive exercises, cognitive training, game technologies and modern pedagogical strategies.

Keywords: attention qualities, psychological mechanisms, stability, mobility, distribution of attention, volume, methodological approaches, cognitive training, interactive methods, motivational factors.

Introduction.

Attention is one of the main functional processes of the human psyche, occupying a central place in its cognitive (cognitive) activity. The processes of acquiring, assimilating and consolidating knowledge by students are directly dependent on the activity and stability of attention. Therefore, it is important to conduct a deep analysis of the psychological mechanisms aimed at developing the qualities of attention - such as strength, stability, divisibility, mobility and volume.

The types and characteristics of attention have been widely studied in psychology. Attention is a process that determines the activity of a person and his selective attitude to objects and phenomena in objective existence. Attention manifests the adaptive function of the human psyche. If there is no attention, then practical activity aimed at a specific goal will not be formed in a person. It is precisely attention that is the basis of human conscious activity, which allows us to act purposefully in certain conditions and situations.

The psychological and pedagogical analysis of attention identifies the main types that characterize its formation and manifestation, each of which is distinguished by its own mechanisms and conditions. In particular, involuntary attention is a type of attention that occurs automatically, independently of the human mind, under the influence of strong and unusual stimuli in the external environment (light, sound, movement, color, smell) or internal psychological

states of the individual (interest, emotional state, instinctive needs). This state is especially pronounced in new information or emergency situations and is characterized by its instability.

Voluntary attention is a type of attention that is consciously controlled by the individual, directed towards a goal, in which the individual tries to concentrate his attention for a certain period of time to perform a given task or activity. The development of voluntary attention directly depends on the volitional qualities of a person, internal motivation, as well as his commitment to the goal. It is by forming this type of attention in the educational process that the student's level of assimilation and depth of thinking are increased.

The third type - post-voluntary attention - is the natural and continuous continuation of attention, initially formed as a conscious action, without elements of volitional activity as a result of increased internal interest in the activity. At this stage, the person's attention is fully focused on the process of activity, and external distractions practically do not affect it. From a pedagogical point of view, it is post-voluntary attention that is considered the most convenient and effective form in ensuring independent and creative thinking of students.

Each of these types of attention is distinguished by its own mechanisms of formation, psychological foundations and significance in the educational process, and their systematic development is one of the important factors ensuring the success of educational activities.

Attention, as one of the main factors that organize human mental activity, is an important cognitive resource that determines the success of students in the learning process. Its effectiveness directly depends not only on the ability to focus attention on an object, but also on how strong, flexible and versatile this attention is. It is emphasized on the basis of scientific sources that attention is expressed through various psychological characteristics, and the level of development of these characteristics significantly affects the individual's attitude to and results of educational activities.

Firstly, intensity is the intensity of a person's attention to a particular object or activity. Strong attention allows a person to fully concentrate on the main task, despite the presence of distracting factors. This is often determined by the level of internal motivation and goal orientation. Secondly, stability is the ability to maintain attention focused on one activity for a long time. This feature helps the student to immerse himself in continuous learning and maintain concentration throughout the lesson. Stable attention is the foundation of thorough knowledge. Third, divisibility refers to the ability to control several activities or information flows at the same time. This skill is especially important when performing

complex tasks, for example, when receiving and recording information through hearing. Fourth, mobility is the ability to quickly, easily and appropriately switch attention from one object to another. This feature is significantly related to adaptability and allows you to easily switch between different topics or activities during the learning process. Fifth, volume refers to the degree to which a person can simultaneously keep in mind several objects or processes. A wide attention span helps to master the educational material, despite its complexity and multifaceted nature. The formation and development of these characteristics are closely related to various psychological mechanisms. Motivation is formed on the basis of internal needs, goals and interests, and determines the level of student's desire for activity. Strong motivation activates attention and allows it to be maintained for a long time.

Emotional state - a person's emotions directly affect the activity of attention. Positive emotions (interest, joy, enthusiasm) enhance attention, while negative emotions (boredom, anxiety, restlessness) weaken it. Therefore, creating an emotionally rich classroom environment is important in developing attention. Voluntariness is the ability of a person to consciously control his attention, focus it on the desired object and maintain it for a long time. Voluntary attention is associated with willpower and requires self-control and dedication to the goal. Psychophysiological foundations - the activity of the human brain, especially the prefrontal cortex (frontal part of the brain), plays a major role in the formation of attention. These areas perform the functions of planning, controlling, maintaining and switching attention. Also, neurotransmitters, especially dopamine and norepinephrine, form the neurobiological basis of the attention process. The development of the above-mentioned properties of attention occurs on the basis of a combination of psychological and physiological factors. By consciously directing this process and enriching it with pedagogical technologies, the quality of the learning process can be significantly improved. In the history of psychological sciences, the concept of attention has been widely studied as one of the central factors regulating a person's cognitive activity and cognitive processes. In particular, the scientific research of scientists such as representatives of the Soviet school of psychology - A.N. Leontyev, L.S. Vygotsky, P.Ya. Galperin, N.F. Dobrynin - deeply analyzed the formation, stages of development and functional characteristics of attention. Their views serve as a solid theoretical basis for modern psychopedagogical approaches[15].

In particular, L.S. Vygotsky in his theory of cultural-historical development interpreted attention as one of the higher psychic functions of a person. In his opinion, attention is formed in the process of ontogenesis with the help of external

social means (including speech), and then becomes a means of internal speech and becomes a consciously controlled activity. Vygotsky sees the transition from natural (biologically based) forms of attention to complex forms based on socio-cultural ones as an important stage in the development of a child. He also considers attention to be directly related to self-regulation, internal control and volitional processes.

Methodological approaches that ensure the formation and development of attention are currently being implemented in the educational process in the following directions:

1. Activity-based approach based on the theory of activity of psychologist A.N. Leontiev. According to him, the psychic functions of a person are formed and improved precisely during activity. Students' participation in the learning process through independent, purposeful and conscious activity creates the necessary conditions for concentrating and stabilizing their attention. Practical tasks, problem situations, project work activate the student's internal motivation and actively use attention resources.

2. The system of training technologies, psychological trainings and special exercises is aimed at developing the characteristics of attention (volume, strength, stability, mobility, divisibility). In trainings, in particular, visual and auditory exercises, reaction speed, accuracy, and quick switching skills are worked on. Through trainings, the student learns to control, manage and activate his attention potential in the necessary situation. These methods are based on the ideas of A.A. Smirnov and P.Ya. Galperin "gradual formation of mental activity".

3. Game methods, didactic games are an effective tool for attracting the student's attention, increasing interest in the lesson and protecting him from distracting factors. With the help of game methods, students are observed to move from involuntary attention to voluntary and post-voluntary stages of attention. Competition, interesting tasks, speed and accuracy in completing tasks - all this creates a state of active attention in the student through the game.

4. Individual approach Since each student has different psychological characteristics, temperament type, personal needs and attention potential, it is of great importance to adapt the methods to the individual. This approach is based on Vygotsky's concept of the 'zone of proximal development' and involves determining the student's capabilities through individual diagnostics and using appropriate methods. In this case, individual indicators related to attention are determined through psychological tests, observations and personal interviews.

5. The use of information technologies, modern digital tools - multimedia presentations, infographics, virtual laboratories, interactive platforms (such as

Kahoot, Quizizz, Mentimeter) - enhances the visual and dynamic components of the learning process. An interactive environment that serves to attract attention, sustain it and increase its performance increases student participation. Information technologies make it possible to implement an individual approach, as well as game elements. Methodological approaches aimed at the formation and development of attention in the learning process should be person-oriented, active, interactive, innovative and technologically based. Through these approaches, not only the process of acquiring knowledge is effectively organized in the student, but also his intellectual potential and ability to think independently are developed.

In modern didactic approaches, methods for developing attention are based on the principles of person-oriented education. This is an important factor not only in the process of obtaining academic knowledge, but also in the formation of the student's ability to think independently and self-manage. A deep analysis of psychological mechanisms and methodological approaches aimed at the formation and development of attention qualities in students allows the teacher to carry out effective pedagogical activities based on an individual approach. This serves as an important factor in the formation of the student as a person, ensuring independent thinking and a high level of mental activity. Attention is one of the main functional processes of the human psyche and plays a central role in its cognitive activity. It is manifested as an internal psychic force that controls, regulates all types of mental activity and increases their effectiveness[14].

Attention is of great importance in all aspects of human activity - in the processes of study, labor, creativity, communication and interaction, and is a necessary condition for its successful implementation. Attention, unlike other mental processes (for example, sensation, perception, thinking, memory, and imagination), does not exist as an independent mental process, but as a mechanism that ensures their activity. This indicates that attention is not a form of "reflection" of mental activity, but a factor that ensures the organized course of other processes. Human intelligence, insight, thoroughness, and active cognitive approach are manifested precisely through the process of attention[42].

In the psychological literature, attention is classified based on various criteria as a complex mental process that regulates a person's cognitive activity. Each type of attention is characterized by its own mechanism of action, content orientation and psychological functions.

1. Types of attention by object of orientation:

- External attention is a state in which a person's attention is directed to objects and phenomena in the environment. External attention is usually based

on stimuli received through the senses. For example, an architect, observing a construction site, directs visual and auditory attention to the objective environment.

- Internal attention is a state in which a person's attention is directed to his own thoughts, experiences, memories and internal reflective states. This type of attention is associated with higher-level thinking and introspective processes and plays an important role in analyzing a problem situation, making decisions or thinking creatively.

2. Types of attention by form of activity:

- Individual attention is the attention of a person focused on the activity he is performing alone. The activity of individual attention is noticeable when a student independently reads a text or works on a problem task.

- Group (collective) attention is a state of general attention that is manifested during the activity carried out as part of a team or group. This form of attention is often formed during interactive methods, discussions and debates, by concentrating the active attention of all participants on one point.

- Attention in the human psyche is a complex mental state that allows you to direct your consciousness to a specific activity or source of information and maintain this focus for a certain period of time. Individual characteristics of attention are one of the important factors determining its effectiveness in the educational process, which are expressed by the following qualities:

- Stability - this quality means the state of maintaining attention on an object or activity continuously, for a certain period of time. Stable attention allows the student to perfectly master the course material, to reflect deeply in the thinking process, and to remember important information. This quality of attention is especially important when acquiring theoretical knowledge and working on scientific texts.

- The quality of attention mobility is associated with the ability to quickly and flexibly switch from one activity to another, from one object to another. Mobility is necessary for a student in complex learning situations, rapid exchange of ideas or parallel performance of educational tasks. It allows you to quickly adapt to changing conditions and orient yourself to new tasks.

- Attention span refers to the ability to focus on multiple activities or streams of information at the same time. This quality is especially important in multitasking activities, for example, when a student needs to take notes while listening to a lecture or analyze graphic and textual information at the same time.

The volume of attention indicates how many objects a person can control at the same time. This quality determines the scope of attention and is especially

important in activities related to visual and logical thinking - for example, when analyzing drawings, tables, diagrams.

The power of attention reflects its intensity and the degree of complete immersion in the activity. Strong attention allows a person to concentrate on the main activity even under the influence of distracting factors. This quality is one of the main psychological indicators that form the will, responsibility and active participation of the student.

These qualities determine the student's activity in cognitive processes, the level of information reception and processing. Also, the development of these characteristics serves to increase the general intellectual potential of the individual and the level of self-control. Individuals with high attention quality are more likely to succeed in complex scientific and creative activities. Thus, attention is an integral part of the human psyche, which ensures the successful course of all other mental processes. A deep study of attention, identifying its types and qualities, is especially important for the effective organization of students' educational activities in the educational process. Therefore, a deep analysis of the psychological essence and various manifestations of attention allows teachers and psychologists to develop effective methods for its management.

Attention ensures the effectiveness of mental activity by directing the human mind to a specific object and concentrating on it. Attention can manifest itself in individual and group (collective) forms. Individual attention is a state of focusing the mind of one person on a specific object and actively paying attention to it, while group or collective attention is a state of directing the mind of a group of people to an object within the framework of general activity and keeping it under collective attention.

Pedagogical conditions aimed at developing attention - through an emotionally rich educational environment, the use of multimodal resources, an individual approach and support for internal motivation - are recognized as an important factor in increasing the effectiveness of teaching and ensuring the intellectual development of the student, since through these conditions the psychophysiological foundations of attention are activated and strengthened.

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